

***In Vivo* effect of Antibiotics on the occurrence of *Azotobacter chroococcum* in the rhizosphere of tomato**

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ABSTRACT

The increasing agricultural reuse of treated effluent serves goals such as promoting sustainable agriculture preserving scarce water resources and maintaining environmental quality. Also, irrigating with wastewater may reduce purification levels and fertilization costs, because soil and crops serve as bio-filters and wastewater contains nutrients. Influence of sewage and sewage components such as soaps, antibiotics, spices, oils and fats, toothpastes, household pesticides, heavy metals etc. on the growth of *Azotobacter chroococcum in vitro* and in rhizosphere and soil was evaluated. Sewage farming is still continued in many towns if the irrigation facilities are not available. Sewage irrigation supported the population of nitrogen fixers such as *Azotobacter*, *Rhizobium* and also fungal organisms used for organic matter decomposition. In the present study *A. Chroococcum* was isolated from the rhizosphere and soil from sewage irrigated fields and the effect of antibiotics such as streptomycin and amoxicillin on nitrogen fixation in tomato inoculated with *A. Chroococcum* was seen. antibiotics reduced streptomycin and amoxicillin *A. Chroococcum* population in the rhizosphere and in soil as well.

Keywords: *Azotobacter*, *Rhizobium*, Sewage farming, streptomycin and amoxicillin

INTRODUCTION

Efficient utilization of water resources is vital to agricultural production. Because water sources are limited and are rather insufficient to meet the long-term requirement of agriculture and consequently affects the rural development. There is also a large gap between the net available water supply and the amount required for intensive cultivation of crop plants. Moreover, natural rainfall is seasonal and generally distributed throughout the country. The technology has brought rapid urbanization and with the multifold expansion of cities, sewage management has become a big task. producing organisms (Kulkarni, 1981).

Sewage components like soaps, household pesticides (DDT, phenyl, Dettol) altered microbial population considerably. Cloth washing soaps and household pesticides affect microbes adversely. *Rhizobium*,

however, responds differently to the sewage components. Phenyl, mustard oil, extracts of cumin, pepper, onion and chillies are harmful whereas sunlight soaps supports the growth of this organism (Kulkarni and Gangawane, 1980, 1982, 1985).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To See the effect of antibiotics on the nitrogen fixation in tomato inoculated with *Azotobacter chroococcum* following methods has been used. One kg of black cotton soil was treated thoroughly with 100 and 500 ppm concentration of streptomycin and amoxicillin. Similarly, soil was also inoculated with *Azotobacter* suspension till complete wet. The soil was again mixed thoroughly with the help of electric homogenizer. The soil thus prepared was placed in earthenware pots.

The seeds of tomato were sown in the pots and again irrigated with antibiotic solutions. The pots treated with only tap water and *Azotobacter* were considered

as control. The pots thus prepared were placed in the Departmental Glass House and watered whenever necessary for four weeks.

Presence of *Azotobacter* in the rhizosphere and soil was determined by serial dilution and plate count method (Timonin, 1940) using nitrogen free glucose medium as has been stated earlier at various growth period of plants. Similarly, counts for other bacteria and fungi were also determined by using Thorton’s Agar and Martins Rose Bengal Agar medium (composition g / litre; KH₂PO₄ 1.0; peptone, 5.0; MgSO₄, 0.5; Dextrose, 10.0; Rose Bengal, 0.033, Agar, 20.0) (Martin, 1950) respectively.

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The results are shown in table-1 and fig-1. It indicates that both the antibiotics i.e streptomycin and amoxicillin reduced *A. Chroococcum* population in the rhizosphere and in soil as well.

Table 1: Effect of Antibiotics on the N₂-fixation in tomato inoculated with *Azotobacter chroococcum*

Antibiotics	Shoot length (cm)	Root length (cm)	Total dry wt (mg / plant)	Nitrogen (%)	log xi – log c DM	log xi-log c (% N)
Streptomycin						
100	15.0	5.5	0304	2.25	0.3067	0.0711
500	14.1	4.8	0242	1.83	0.2077	-0.0185
Amoxicillin						
100	15.0	5.5	0160	1.41	0.0280	-0.1318
500	12.0	6.0	0084	0.55	0.2518	-0.5406
Control	21.2	3.5	0150	1.91	0.0000	0.0000
C.D. (P = 0.05)			98.56	0.75		

Fig. 1: Effect of antibiotics. on N₂ Fixation in tomato inoculated with *A. chroococcum*

The number was highly reduced due to amoxicillin when compared with control. Other bacteria also showed more or less same results. Fungal population on the other hand was increased both in the rhizosphere and soil due to these antibiotics. Two concentrations of streptomycin and amoxicillin was taken as 100 and 500ppm. Shoot length, root length, dry weight and nitrogen fixation in tomato was decreased in both the antibiotics as compared to control.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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